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RHBDD family expression changes in AD iPS models.

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Our aim was identification of molecules with biochemical function with potential to influence amyloid fibril interactions, stability or polymerization, including molecules with redox modulating functions like PDIs. Expression of RHBDD family genes, whose involvement in AD biology was brought to our attention following literature search of PDI type amyloid regulation, was more frequently and more significantly perturbed in AD than was PDIs.